

WORK LIFE BALANCE AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE OF MEDICAL PERSONNELS AT KENYATTA NATIONAL HOSPITAL, KENYA

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Abstract: This study evaluated work life balance effect on medical personnel employee performance at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. The objective with certainty is determining the effect of flexible work conditions, leave management and career development on employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. Discrepancy theory, spill over theory and compensation theory were employed. Nurses and doctors which was be descriptively design at Kenyatta National Hospital Kenya were covered and a sample size of one hundred and sixty was used based on seventy five doctors (75) and eighty five (85) nurses to be drawn from the hospital; selected through stratified random sampling design. Primary data was relied upon through questionnaires. Validity of the research instruments were be assessed using expert opinion and pilot test while reliability of research construct ascertained via Cronbach Alpha test with a threshold of 0.7. The outcome from the multiple regression depicted that flexible work conditions, leave management and career development had positive and significant effect on employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. To this effect the study recommends that in order to experience improvements on efficient and effective delivery of service at the Kenyatta National Hospital, more flexible work conditions should be implemented and existing ones is strengthened to ensure easy adaptability of the medical personnel to new environmental changes for best medical practices.

Keywords: Work Life Balance, Flexible Work Conditions, Leave Management, Career Development and Employee Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

In an ever changing environment which is based on several changes and transformation, as such organizations strive towards having optimal performance which is determined by employee performance (Al-Hawary & AL-Hamwan, 2017). Due to the dynamic nature of the operating environments, organizations in the health sector have since come to the contention that services have to be provided in line with stakeholders' needs and expectations. Therefore, employee performance stands as a critical factor to these organizations. In general, the whole performances of firms are dependent on personnel who are notably affected by several factors which can be family or work related and in some cases both. Thus, the importance of work life balance which entails efficiency while enhancing the yield of the employees. The fulfillment of employees is reflected in overall performances of organizations (Odengo & Kiiru, 2019). Organizations therefore ought to consider work life balance which has become paramount over time.

In the context of Africa, importance has been placed on leadership and dispositional variables as a result of the dynamic nature of the workplace (Kangure, 2014). Employees are considered to be of importance and as such perform key roles towards the success of an organization and these cannot be over emphasized. Employees perform different roles which are largely categorized as work related and leisure or social activities related, which bring about contending needs as each title held by an individual (employee) is accompanied with a degree of obligations or responsibility (Odengo & Kiiru, 2019). These responsibilities necessitate some level of balance across the various segments of life in a faultless manner. As such priority is required to be maintained in the execution of certain duties. Work-life balance is well thought-out as a division of the focus and time of a person between daily leisure and working activities. Leisure activities largely entail quality time with friends and family members. Notably, prioritizing between lifestyle and career ambition is required. Lifestyle aspects span from spirituality, health, leisure pleasure as well as family (Heathfield, 2016).

In Kenyan, employee performance has been recognized by institutions as a key factor of achieving set goals and objectives (Auka & Nyangau, 2020). Their success is therefore dependent on employee performance and as such poor performance is unfavourable to organizational goals and objectives achievement. Therefore, employees' attitudes regarding their and personal lives are attributes of balance in work-life (Wainaina, 2015). The balance of work-life relates to pattern of employees allocating more time on work as compared to their private lives and these two components are constantly contending and tangled. In a situation of the existence of competing needs, there arises conflict (Swarnalatha & Rajalakshmi, 2016). Work can be voluntary or remunerated. Leisure is considered as the opposite of work as it is a period where one (worker) makes a decision on what to do with his/her time. The two spheres of work life balance and the underlying conflict revolve around the interference of the life and work and vice versa (Chungo & Anyieni, 2019). Among the aforementioned interferences, the intrusion of work on life occurs more often as compared to work being hindered or interfered with life. These conflicts manifest as changes in job satisfaction, work stress, turnover commitment as well as life satisfaction.

The National Kenyatta Hospital being the first established referral hospital in Kenya provides referral services to people in Africa and East Africa (Willis, 2015). It consists of 1157 medical personnel who attend to about 3000 patients in a day. The medical personnel comprise of 100 doctors, 800 nurses, 130 pharmacists, 70 laboratory technician, 50 clinical officers and 5 dentists (Wambura, 2016). Medical personnel at KNH are entitled to the KNH provident fund which was established in July 1991. The KNH provident fund comprises of 5% of the medical personnel's salary and a 10% contribution from KNH. After retirement, all of the medical employees are entitled to both contributions while medical employees that do not retire but leave voluntarily are not entitled to the contributions (Collins, Njeru & Meme, 1996).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Healthcare personnel stand as the hearts and hands of the health sector. As such, the management of work life balance that is inherent in modern organizations is of key importance. This is in view of employee performance as well as work life balances relationships which in turn determine the performance of institutions in overall (Musyoka & Kimencu, 2020). As such, it is of importance to the achievement of set goals and objectives in an organizational setting. Notably, having a balance with work and personal life has been a difficult situation faced by medical employees and by extension organizations. Balancing between personal or family demands against that of work has been a constant struggle which brought about the emergence of work-family conflict (Auka and Nyangau (2020).

Notably, several studies have contributed in terms of how employee performance is affected by work life balance. Wainaina (2015) study's reported that Kenya's universities' employee performance is affected by career development positively. Mulanya and Kagiri (2018) gathered from their study that the flexibility of work conditions negatively affect the performance of employee and should not be utilized by organizations. Musyoka and Kimencu (2020) depicted that performances of employee is significantly determined through career development indeed. Auka and Nyangau (2020) in their study on referral hospitals in Kenya reported that leave management which includes annual leave, maternity leave and sick leave has a significant effect on organizational performance. Furthermore, Begall, Breeschoten, Lippe and Poortman (2020) revealed from their study findings that family leave provision influences employee performance.

With respect to certain studies, the context of the subject matter of the balance of personal life and work as well as employee performance has been carried out differently. Dissanayaka and Ali (2013) reveal that the nexus between work life balances and employees performances is positive. The research focused on correlation analysis specifically to organizations in Sri Lanka. Wainaina (2015) documented that career development positively affects organizational commitment. The study despite being on Kenya, the focus was the educational sector and specifically private and public universities. Auka *et al.* (2020) concluded that leave management is significant in improving performance. Despite focusing on a referral hospital,

the study concentrated largely on organizational performance as a whole whereas this study will narrowed down to employee performance which is a key component of the overall performance of an organization. Thus, each study is unique to countries and institution and characterized by peculiar characteristics.

In addition, some of the studies done in connection to work life balance and employee performance have underlying conceptual gaps in that some key variables were isolated. The study by Chungo and Anyieni (2019) focused on leave management in terms of paternity/maternity leave, annual leave, sick leave and bereavement leave while neglecting other work life balance factors. Begall *et al.* (2020) focused on family leave provision and the effect on employee performance but isolated other variables such as career development and flexible work condition. In addition, Musyoka *et al.* (2020) directed their work how career development influenced employee performance in terms of seminars, trainings and conferences while isolating other work life balance factors which are leave management, flexible work conditions amongst others which this present study considered. In view of the preceding gaps, this study determined how Kenyatta National Hospital performance of their employee is affected by work life balance of medical personnel in Kenya.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

1.3.1 General Objective

The general objective is to investigate the effect of work life balance on employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital.

1.3.1 Specific Objectives

Particularly, the research aimed:

- i. To institute flexible work conditions effect with respect to employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya.
- ii. To determine how leave management affect the performance of employee of medical personnel at KNH, Kenya.
- iii. To examine the effect of career development on employees performances of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya.

1.4 Research Questions

Answers to these questions were provided:

- i. What effect does flexible work conditions has on employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya?
- ii. Does leave management have an effect on employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya?
- iii. Is there any career development effect with respect to employee performances of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

The value-percept disparity model is another name for the discrepancy theory. Wilcock and Wright first introduced it in 1991. The theory asserts that fulfillment derived is dependent on the level by which outcomes that individuals think they derive from work are corresponding with the outcomes pursued in work (Rode, 2004). This is based on three (3) key factors or attributes which are; an explicit or implicit value standard, the perception of some of the job aspects as well as a conscious judgment of the possible discrepancies (gap) across one's values and perceptions. Views relates to being in the know of something existing and also its underlying cognitive judgment, that is, in line with recognized standards. Value preposition is regarded to be the estimation of some judged relationships to the normative standards of one, value is often regarded as that which an individual view as conducive to his or her welfare” (Wilcock & Wright, 1991).

Spill Over Theory holds the assertion that several conditions exist under spillover emanating between the micro system of the family as well as that of the system at large. Such relationship can either be direct or inverse. Inverse nexus can occur in a situation that work and family interactions are structured in a rigid manner in terms of scope and time which spill-over

regarding energy, time and behavior has high likelihood of being an inverse one. A positive nexus can be expected in cases that flexible work and family interactions as this provides allowance for integrating and overlapping of work by employees with respect to time and space. This therefore, leads to a positively influenced spill over that is considered importance in achieving the balance of life at work (Greenhaus, Collins & Shaw, 2003).

Compensation Theory as introduced by Wicklund in 1986 is based on the idea of introducing opportunities and incentives as a way of preventing certain unfortunate experiences in an organization. It can vary depending on the scenario, it is unique to hard working employer and a committed family individual who places family above all else, the responses in the two situation will however be different (Edwards & Rothbard, 2000). An unfulfilled family individual will compensate himself by focusing on work and other aspects of life while an unfulfilled career individual will compensate himself by focusing on family (Dixon & Sagas, 2007). Employees who work in an organization tends to function properly and carry out their duties when they receive feedback and compensation for their performance (Wicklund, 1986)

2.2 Empirical Review

Simonetta and Manfred (2010) determined work life balance effect on performance (staff experience) in the context of Oxford Brookes University through their examination. A sample of four hundred and ninety-two (492) respondents was used as drawn from staff of the oxford brooks university. Findings show that career development influences the performance of employees with such an organization. It was observed that it is of significance to have a balanced personal life and paid work condition as it ensures performances of employees. Oxford Brookes University was however the focus of the aforesaid study, while this current study focus was referral hospitals, Kenya.

Dissanayaka and Ali (2013) studied the empirically link between work life balance and employee performance where Sri Lanka was the focus of the study. The study used a sample size of 96 respondents, all of whom were chosen from the workforce. With the aid of research questionnaires, data was gathered. Results showed a positive relationship between leave management and employee performance, according to Pearson moment correlation. The study provided the recommendation that organizations should put systematic effort towards the improvement of employee work life balance as this in turn will bring about higher employee performances. The focus of the study was however organizations (Sri Lanka) via correlation analysis. The previous study only utilized correlation analysis which reflects the level of associations among variables unlike Regression analysis which tests statistical significance. The present study apart from provide evidence from the Kenyan context further applied both correlation and regression analyses model.

Ojo, Salau and Falola (2014) in determining the result of the effect of WLB on EP, carried out a research study on the power, education and banking sectors of the Nigerian economy. Using primary quantitative data, the data was gathered from both managers and junior employees working at the three sectors. The respondents' constituted 586 respondents in the banking sector, 531 respondents in the educational sector and 507 respondents in the power sector. Utilizing the model of multiple regression with which revealed that work conditions has a highly significant effect in the employees' performance at the three sectors. However, the previous work was specifically conducted on three main sectors in Nigeria which makes the results of the study not generic. Thus, this present study focuses on how the performance of employees is affected by work life balance in a Kenyan context.

The study done by Fapohunda (2014) explored the underlying WLB on employees productivity with emphasize on the Chinese health section. The study labeled employees productivity based on employee turnover and absenteeism. Using descriptive research design with the use of questionnaires, a total of 200 respondents sampled across the sectors were employed. A closed ended structured questionnaire was used to collate responses which was the data used for analysis. The analysis of the collated responses discovered a significant positive nexus between work conditions and productivity based on employee turnover and absenteeism. The aforesaid study's analysis and conclusion was however based on China's health sector while this present study explores the way work life balance determine employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya.

Vishwa *et al.* (2015) explored the manner in which job satisfaction of employees and performance is affected by policies of WLB. The evaluation employed the use of 240 respondents sampled across managers and employees. Correlation analysis was done through SPSS from the responses gathered from the 240 respondents. The outcome established significant link between work conditions, employee (job satisfaction) and employee performances. The aforesaid research was however based on analysis of correlation, whereas, this present used multiple regression in addition therefore, filling the gaps.

Mulanya and Kagiri (2018) assessed work life balance effects on employee performances with focus on CRA. The study's target population, recruited from the Commission, consisted of 68 employees. The study discovered that employee breaks (leave) had a significant effect on workers' performance. This is as employees felt re-energized after annual leave which makes them to work better. The fact that the employees were not denied any benefits as a result of taking time off showed that they were more dedicated. It was recommended that the commission should enhance leave packages for purposes of suiting the current life styles of employees. Employee assistance programs should be provided such as child care unity as this will ensure that employees concentrate rather than being bothered about their children. The previous study's target population was drawn from Commission on Revenue Allocation while this current study differs as its target population was drawn from Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya.

Chungo *et al.* (2019) studied employee leave influence on the performance organizations with emphasis on Rift Valley Bottlers. The study used the variables paternity/maternity, annual, sick and bereavement leaves and how they affect organizational performances. Locke's Range of Affect Theory, Herzberg's Two Factor Theory as well as Job Characteristics Model were adopted. A target demographic of 69 respondents was selected from Rift Valley Bottlers' various departments using a descriptive survey research technique, using a census approach. The study found out that leave significantly influences performances of firms. The study recommends that annual leave should be offered to workers by Rift Valley Bottlers Limited. Support should be provided to an employee who is bereaved. Sick leave period can be open and this can depend on the nature and degree of the illness. Notably, the study only focused on leave management, other vital aspects of WLB such as career development/work conditions were isolated but included in the current study. Additionally, the previous study focused on Rift Valley Bottlers whereas this current study differs as it focuses on Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya.

Auka *et al.* (2020) studied the effect of work conditions on organizational performances for HBCRH, Kenya. The study focused on leave management and work conditions and how they are effectual on the performance of hospitals. With the use research of descriptive design, a population of 696 was covered and a sample size (based on stratified random sampling) comprising of 254 employees was drawn. The response rate was reported at 89.4% which translates to 227 respondents. Based on Pearson correlation analysis, it was concluded that work conditions and leave are important in predicting performance for HBCRH. Rather than applying only correlation analysis just like the aforementioned study, this present study used both correlation and regression analyses.

Musyoka and Kimencu (2020) studied work life balance influence on employee performances in public hospitals with focus on Machakos Level 5 Hospital. The research applied stratified random sampling where 200 respondents formed the sample which cut across doctors, nurses, as well as Support staff. While using multiple regression analysis, exposition from the outcomes noted that work conditions holds strong effect with EP. It was recommended that work conditions be enhanced continuously by managers. Despite the previous study contributing to existing literature, the focus was level 5 hospitals in Machakos and also further isolated leave policy which is one of the key elements of work life balance. This present study differs as it focused on KNH and also include the leave management as one of its specific objectives

Begall *et al.* (2020) evaluated the nexus between supplemental family leave provision and employees' performances. The study sought to assess family supplemental leave provision effect and how it leads to higher work efforts as well as extra-role behaviors by workers. Signaling theory and organizational support theory were used to support the nexus between supplemental and EP with the consideration of increase in organizational commitment. The test for hypothesis was done in view of European multilevel organization-data which was based on 11,011 employees cutting across 869 teams or departments from 259 corporations. Outcome reflect employees perform better in context when they think that additional family leave is available; this is partly related to a rise in organizational commitment. The aforementioned study adds to existing studies, but the analysis was based on data from European multilevel organizations. This present study is different in that the focus is Kenya (which is categorized as a developing country) and specifically on KNH which is the first and largest referral hospital in Kenya.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current study was conducted within the parameters of descriptive research design, which is justified by the fact that this research aims to determine the effect of work-life balance on employee performance and is, therefore, linked to the primary premise of descriptive research design (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). The target study population was medical personnel of Kenyatta National Hospital, consisting of nurses and doctors. Number of doctors in the hospital is 747 while that of nurses is 845 which make it a total of 1592. Purposive sampling was employed for the investigation as this allows a

researcher to apply discretion and personal judgment to select a sample based on who will best provide the needed data (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2013). The sample size consists of 75 doctors and 85 nurses who are medical personnel at the Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. Thus, the unit of the sample size was 160. Employee performance in the context of Referral hospitals in Kenya is modeled as a function of work life balance (flexible work conditions, leave management and career development) as modeled below:

$$EP = \beta_0 + \beta_1FC + \beta_2LM + \beta_3CD + \varepsilon$$

Key:

EP = Employee Performance

FC = Flexible Work Conditions

LM = Leave Management

CD = Career Development

ε = Error-term

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Coefficients

β_0 = Constant

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Response Rate

The outcome of the response and non-response rates is shown in Table 4.1 for purposes of assessing the rate of response from the medical workers at Kenyatta National Hospital.

Table 4.1: Response Rate

Rates	Frequency	Percent
Response	160	100%
Non-Response	0	0%
Total	160	100

Source: Survey Data (2021)

The study had a 100 percent response rate and a 0 percent non-response rate, respectively. Cooper and Schindler (2009) suggested that return rate spanning from 50 percent or higher is sufficient for investigational purposes. As a result, the research outcome revealed a response rate of 100% return rate, which is high and recommended analysis.

4.2 Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's Alpha, which recommended a coefficient range of 0 to 1.00, was used to determine the study instrument's reliability. Table 4.2 depicts the outcome which used a coefficient of 0.7 or higher.

Table 4.2: Reliability Analysis

	Reliability Cronbach's Alpha
Employee Performance	.782
Flexible Work Condition	.876
Leave Management	.776
Career Development	.814

Source: Study Data (2022)

Employee performance, flexible work conditions, leave management, and career development all had Alpha values of 0.782, 0.876, 0.776, and 0.814, respectively, according to the results shown in Table 4.2. As a result, the reliability coefficient values for the variables utilized in the investigation as 0.7 and above reflects adequacy in the measures the research construct (Rousson *et al.*, 2012).

4.3. Inferential Analysis

Inferential statistics was conducted to draw out conclusion on the research problem which was carried out using multiple regression frameworks. As informed by the specific objective and the study research question, the assessment was conducted.

4.3.1 Model Summary

The model summary indicating the R square and Adjusted R square is presented in Table 4.3 below.

Table 4.3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.894 ^a	.825	.721	.47977

Source: Study Data (2022)

The R value 0.894 reflects strong positive correlation existing among WLB and EP of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. The R-square of 0.825 shows that all work life balance measurement accounted for only 82.5% variation in the employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. This means that 82.5% changes in employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya is captured the explanatory constructs. 17.5% variation in employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya is unexplained in the model. Thus, 17.5% changes in employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital is explained by other factors aside work life balance.

4.3.2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

This was done towards determining the model (variables) significance as depicted in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.316	3	4.772	20.731	.000 ^b
	Residual	35.908	156	.230		
	Total	50.224	159			

Source: Study Data (2021)

This analysis shows how the predictors influenced employee performance. 20.731 as F statistics was established. Hence, since significance was established, WBL (flexible work conditions, leave management and career development) jointly and significantly affect employee performance.

4.3.3 Multiple Regression Analysis

In order to ascertain the effect of the explanatory variables on the explained variable, multiple regression analysis was conducted. The output of the regression analysis is presented in Table 4.5

Table 4.5: Regression Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.938	.168		5.565	.000
	FC	.173	.069	.207	2.504	.013
	LM	.235	.070	.280	3.366	.001
	CD	.187	.078	.181	2.405	.017

Source: Study Data (2022)

$$EP = 0.938 + 0.173FC + 0.235LM + 0.187CD + \varepsilon$$

Where:

EP = Employee Performance

FC = Flexible Work Conditions

LM = Leave Management

CD = Career Development

4.4 Interpretation of Findings

As demonstrated in Table 4.5, the research outcome indicated the effect each of the explanatory variable have on employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. 0.938 as the constant coefficient based on 0.000. This means that employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya would be positive without the different work life balance components employed in the study.

The study established that flexible work conditions have positive and significant effect on EP of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. This is shown by the coefficient of 0.173 and the probability value 0.013. This implies that a 1% improvements towards flexible work conditions would lead to an increase of 0.173% in employee performances of KNH. The outcome of the study could be attributed to the work conditions of the personnel which allow them the freedom to operate giving the dynamic nature of situations surrounding the hospital environment. Therefore, changing level of technology allows for easy adaptability thus, making the personnel more productive at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. The outcome of the study is consistent with Ojo, Salau and Falola (2014) who found that work conditions has a highly significant effect in the performance of the employees at educational sector, power sector and banking sector in Nigeria. Also, Fapohunda (2014) observed strong relationship between work conditions and productivity based on employee turnover and absenteeism. Vishwa *et al.* (2015) strong nexus between work conditions and employee job satisfaction/employee performance. Musyoka and Kimencu (2020) established that work conditions had a significant positive effect and relationship with employee performance.

Leave management revealed a positive coefficient of (0.235) which is statistically significant in relation to the employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. This denotes that a 1% increase in leave management would result into an increase in the employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya by 0.235%. This is evaluated by the probability value 0.001. The significance of the study can be attributed to the effectiveness of the hospital leave management which allows personnel to rest and take part in other career development ventures thereby improving their delivery skills. Thus, a relaxed mind brings forth deep thoughts of innovation and creativity thereby improving the personnel productivity at the hospital. The outcome aligns with Mulanya and Kagiri (2018) who found that employee breaks (leave) strongly affects employee performances. This is as employees felt re-energized after annual leave which makes them to work better. Chungo *et al.* (2019) that leave significantly influences performances of firms. Additionally, Auka *et al.* (2020) reported that leave management has significance in the improvement of health workers' performance. Begall *et al.* (2020) in their research established that availability of supplemental family leave leads to positive employee contextual performances which are partially attributed to increase in organization commitment.

Furthermore, career development positively impacts EP of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. The positive coefficient of 0.187 was realized meaning that a 1% increase in career development would increase the employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital by 0.187%. The evaluation of the positive and significant relationship is revealed by the probability 0.017. This is attributed to the inculcation of new skills and techniques which facilitates the efficiency of these medical personnel as such, enhances the performance of the medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital. Therefore, no employee improves in skills and in the discharge of effective duty without updated skills hence career development of the medical personnel plays a crucial role in the delivery of their responsibilities. The findings of the study aligned with Simonetta and Manfred (2010) who noted that career development influences the performance of employees with such an organization. Wainaina (2015) established that career development positively affects organizational commitment in private and public universities.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The investigation concluded that work life balance which constituted flexible work conditions, leave management and career development significantly affects employees performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. It is concluded that flexible work conditions performs vital role towards determining employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. This means that flexible work conditions allows the medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital adapt to any innovation in the hospital that enhances the delivery of their duty and hence general performance of the medical personnel.

Leave management had significant prediction of employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. The study concluded that leave management is an indispensable element in determining employee performance of

medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. The research concluded that leave management energizes medical personnel of the hospital hence making them more committed to their duties knowing full well that all benefits accruing to such leave are not denied of them.

The research outlined that career development plays a significant role in the willpower of employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. In view of this finding, the research concluded that career development is of the essence in elucidating employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. Thus, none of these employees' skills are improved effectively without updated skills hence career development of the medical personnel plays a crucial role in the delivery of their responsibilities at Kenyatta National Hospital.

5.2 Policy Recommendations

WLB components used were flexible work conditions, leave management and career development and they had significant effect towards EP of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital. To this effect, the research concluded that flexible work conditions had positive and significant effect on employee performance of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital. Therefore, in order to improve on efficiency and effectiveness in the delivery of service at the Kenyatta National Hospital, more flexible work conditions should be implemented and existing ones be strengthened to ensure easy adaptability of the medical personnel to new environmental changes for best medical practices.

Leave management is significant in predicting EP of medical personnel at Kenyatta National Hospital. The study recommends opines that hospital authorities responsible for leave management should make conscientious efforts in repackaging leave incentives that suites the best life style of the medical personnel towards enhancing productivity at the Kenyatta National Hospital.

Career development significantly affects employees' performance of medical personnel at KNH. Therefore, the research recommends that the management of Kenyatta National Hospital should ensure consistent training of medical personnel to catch up with global best practice which would enhance the performances of the medical staff in the delivery of their service. This can be encouraged through the establishment of post training medical centers where medical personnel are expected to have rotational training in new endemic and pandemic outbreaks.

5.3 Suggestions for Future Research

The study was on the effect of work life balance and its effect on employees' performance at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya, the study suggests that other studies can be focused on other Hospitals in the different Counties in Kenya. Additionally, other studies can be carried out work life balance and employees' performance in other organizations aside hospital.

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